

GL MICAVE

D1.4 Data gathering and curation mechanisms

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Executive summary

The primary goal of Deliverable D1.4 is the mechanism for the curation of structured omics data for use within GLOMICAVE. This involves the transformation of raw data, which has been downloaded from the various public omics repositories, into an appropriate standardized form. These are then quality controlled and merged into a combined dataset.

Deliverable D1.4 is pivotal in the function of the GLOMICAVE platform as it provides the bulk of the structured data on which the relationship discovery analyses are performed in Work Package 4. It uses a flexible pipeline model, based on the widely adopted Galaxy platform.

Proposed pipelines covering transcriptomics and epigenomics are included within this deliverable to validate the proposed approach. It is expected that further pipelines will be developed on an on-going basis to support additional omics platforms and types of analyses.

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Introduction

This task focuses on processing of raw data, with format conversion, filtering, normalization, quality control and aggregation, to produce standardized datasets for further analysis.

The first step is to determine a standardized set of processing steps with defined tools and configurations for each data type (RNA-Seq, Mass spectrometry etc.). This includes format conversion, filtering, normalization, quality control and aggregation.

For each conceptual processing step, a set of defined tools will be identified, and one or more sets of configuration parameters defined.

An API for pipeline definition will be created, allowing the specific combination of processing tools and their associated settings to be defined for each dataset.

The primary goal of Deliverable D1.4 is the mechanism for the curation of structured omics data for use within GLOMICAVE. This involves the transformation of raw data, which has been downloaded from the various public omics repositories, into an appropriate standardized form, suitable for merging into a combined dataset. These datasets are then accessed using various statistics collected during processing, using configurable thresholds. Approved datasets are then combined and sent to for downstream analyses.

Deliverable D1.4 uses a flexible pipeline model, based on the widely adopted Galaxy platform. This pipeline approach was chosen since there are often several steps involved in data conversion and in ensuring that the data which is delivered for downstream analysis is high quality and complete.

Section 1 introduces the context around this Deliverable, and how it will integrate with the other parts of GLOMICAVE. Section 2 describes the implementation approach chosen in detail. Section 3 describes the validation for this approach using example pipelines for transcriptomics and epigenomics.

1. Overview

1.1 Source Data Repositories

The identification of source repositories for the various omics was made within Deliverable D1.1. One important criterion for repository selection was the availability of a formal access application programming interface (API), to ensure reliable integration over the long term.

1.2 Data Integration Format

The majority of the omics datasets used within the GLOMICAVE platform are inherently representing a quantity of specific molecules, such as transcript expression levels, protein abundance or metabolite concentrations. Therefore, a matrix structure with the quantification of each determined entity (transcript, protein, or metabolite) for each sample is a natural representation. This structure has the advantage that it can be easily consumed by the other work packages and is a natural format for Machine Learning approaches.

Genomics data, although inherently more discrete, can generally be represented in the same structure. This can be a binary representation (e.g., presence / absence of a specific gene) or numeric (e.g., reference vs alternate allele counts at a specific locus).

1.3 Motivation

A process to convert raw data, such as sequencing reads or MS (Mass Spectrometry) spectra, into this standardized quantitative form is required within the GLOMICAVE platform for two main reasons.

The primary reason is that most of the omics repositories mainly focus on the storage of raw data. They frequently do not support processed data at all or consider it as an optional component of datasets. Thus, quantitative data is not available from the repository for many omics datasets.

The second reason is that the results of some analysis pipelines, particularly those using sequencing data like RNA-Seq or proteomics, are inherently connected to the reference sequences and tools used for the analysis. Since these reference sequences and tools are incrementally improved over time, the various datasets are likely to use different reference sequences and/or tools. However, the integration of quantitative datasets created using different references and/or tools is challenging. It is therefore generally preferred to re-run the quantification process using a single reference and standardized pipeline before dataset integration and further analysis. Thus, even in cases where quantitative data is available, it still cannot be used in the GLOMICAVE platform.

1.4 Relationship to Other Work Packages

Responsibility for building the Knowledge Graph based on structured omics datasets retrieved from external repositories is divided between Work Package 1 (Tasks 1.3 and 1.4) and Work Package 4, as can be seen in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: The data flows between Tasks 1.3 and 1.4 within WP1 and WP4, as well as the External Repositories and Knowledge Graph.

The Work Package 1 flow is divided between Task 1.3 and Task 1.4 as follows:

- Task 1.3:
 - Repository integration: Querying for and retrieving new datasets from the respective repositories.
 - Metadata Standardization: Converting the repository-specific metadata structure into a standardized form.
 - Transfer to Work Package 4: If a dataset includes quantitative data, Task 1.3 can transfer it to Work Package 4 directly. Otherwise, it is forwarded to Task 1.4 for conversion to quantitative form before it can be forwarded to Work Package 4.

- Task 1.4:
 - Determining which processing pipelines and parameters should be used based on the dataset metadata and selecting the automated pipeline to process the data.
 - Executing the selected processing pipeline
 - Performing quality control by e.g., checking statistics from the processing pipeline against configured thresholds.
 - If these quality checks succeed, the quantitative dataset is returned to Task 1.3. Otherwise, the dataset is marked as failed, and can optionally be checked manually, which may also include processing it again e.g., using the different pipeline.

2. Implementation

2.1 Data Processing Framework

2.1.1 Requirements

A major challenge of this Deliverable is handling the variety of omics and measurement platforms involved, and thus the number of processing pipelines needed. The heterogenous nature between the different omics and even within a single omics requires a high level of flexibility in the tools/pipelines used to process the data.

The GLOMICAVE project aims to integrate data from Genomics, Transcriptomics, Epigenomics, Proteomics and Metabolomics. Raw data from each of these omics is currently produced by various measurement platforms, from different manufacturers and using different principles. Furthermore, this diversity can be expected to generally increase in future, as new technologies and measurement platforms continue to be developed.

2.1.2 Approach

To handle this variety, both now and in the future, a flexible framework for defining processing pipelines is vital. After evaluating a selection of possible solutions to deal with the particular challenges within the project, it was decided to adapt the well-established Galaxy framework to define the pipelines. The use of the Galaxy framework helps to resolve several potential long-term sustainability issues:

- Allows pipelines to be quickly designed & modified without needing programming expertise. Although this criterion is unimportant during the development phase, allowing modification and improvement by non-IT experts will help ensure the long-term sustainability of the GLOMICAVE platform.
- Ensures new tools are available: new tools, whether needed to support new omics platform or keep up with improved analysis techniques for established platforms, have historically been integrated quickly by the Galaxy community.

Furthermore, the use of the Galaxy framework avoids several potential technical issues

- The Galaxy framework is designed to scale from small deployments for test purposes, to large distributed computational clusters and is thus inherently flexible enough to enable deployment on the cloud-based GLOMICAVE platform without large development efforts.
- It provides a selection of APIs that enables automated triggering of pipelines, e.g., based on new data becoming available from the repositories.

2.1.3 Pipeline and Parameter Selection

The main criterion for the selection of the pipeline is which of the omics is being measured, with the measurement platform also as an important determining factor. Specific details such as the lab protocol used to prepare the samples for measurement may also play a role.

The genotype (e.g., species) of the sample is also critical, since it determines the reference sequences used, which is one of the most important pipeline parameters.

These metadata attributes are provided for each dataset by Task 1.3.

3. Development and Validation

3.1 Pipeline Development

The initial validation involved deploying a Galaxy instance to a development server. This instance was then used to implement and test specific candidate transcriptomic and epigenetic pipelines. These omics were chosen as the initial focus since they represent the vast majority of non-quantitative public datasets across all the omics, and thus offer the greatest benefit for bulk data analyses within the downstream work packages. Nonetheless, it is expected that the same technical approach will be suitable for, for example, microarray analysis and proteomics.

These pipelines were designed to use state-of-the-art tools for each step. In cases where several comparable tools are available, we base our decision on broad adoption by the bioinformatics community and published comparisons. If no clear benefit could be established, we implemented multiple pipelines and plan to assess their performance using the scaled-up future deployment within the GLOMICAVE platform.

3.2 Testing Datasets

As part of the testing process, a small number of suitable sequencing runs from tomato were downloaded from the ENA and processed.

Each candidate RNA-Seq pipeline was validated by processing the first 1,000,000 reads from one run (SRR10321315) within a Low Nitrogen experiment (PRJNA578768) on Tomato. For the epigenetics pipeline, one run (SRR13189560) from experiment (PRJNA682315) investigating GOLDEN2-like Transcription Factors was used. Since these validations used only a small fraction of each run, they were not expected to be biologically informative, but were still sufficient to allow initial validation that the pipeline works as expected.

The reference genome, annotation and transcriptome were downloaded from the Sol Genomics Network (ITAG v3.2).

3.3 Transcriptomics Validation

Although the wet-lab steps of RNA-Seq are by now largely routine and standardized, the downstream bioinformatics often varies. This analysis can be performed using a variety of approaches, and within each approach, most steps can be implemented using diverse tools. These approaches offer various trade-offs regarding computational cost, potential bias, tolerance to poor dataset quality, tolerance to poor reference sequences and/or annotations.

The three approaches that were implemented were:

- Alignment against the genome, assignment using the annotation and counting: An example version of this pipeline is shown in Figure 2. Analysis Statistics are shown in Table 1, with corresponding results Table 2.
- Alignment against the transcriptome and counting: Figure 5 shows a version of this approach, using Bowtie2 as the aligner. Results are shown in Table 3.
- Pseudo-Alignment against the transcriptome and expression estimation: These pipelines are trivial and thus not shown. Results using Salmon are shown in Table 4 and corresponding results using Kallisto are shown in Table 5.

Figure 2: RNA-Seq Pipeline for Genome Alignment approach.

Table 1: Example Fragment Assignment statistics for RNA-Seq analysed by the Genome Alignment approach.

Assigned	1139147
Unassigned_Unmapped	218705
Unassigned_Read_Type	0
Unassigned_Singleton	0
Unassigned_MappingQuality	0
Unassigned_Chimera	0
Unassigned_FragmentLength	0
Unassigned_Duplicate	0
Unassigned_MultiMapping	99467
Unassigned_Secondary	0
Unassigned_NonSplit	0
Unassigned_NoFeatures	490588
Unassigned_Overlapping_Length	0
Unassigned_Ambiguity	93471

Table 2: Subset of Results for RNA-Seq analysed by the Genome Alignment approach, showing gene name and assigned read counts.

Solyc00g005040.3.ITAG3.2	4
Solyc00g005050.3.ITAG3.2	60
Solyc00g005096.1.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g005283.1.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g005285.1.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g005470.2.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g005840.3.ITAG3.2	94
Solyc00g005850.2.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g005890.3.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g005900.2.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g005907.1.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g006490.3.ITAG3.2	80
Solyc00g006590.2.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g006800.3.ITAG3.2	76
Solyc00g006805.1.ITAG3.2	2
Solyc00g006810.3.ITAG3.2	40
Solyc00g006820.3.ITAG3.2	50
Solyc00g006830.3.ITAG3.2	104
Solyc00g006840.3.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g006867.1.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g006903.1.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g007560.2.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g007555.1.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g007600.2.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g007925.1.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g008055.1.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g008070.2.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g008165.1.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g008570.2.ITAG3.2	64
Solyc00g009020.3.ITAG3.2	330
Solyc00g009040.3.ITAG3.2	0
Solyc00g009050.2.ITAG3.2	6
Solyc00g009060.3.ITAG3.2	30
Solyc00g009090.3.ITAG3.2	6
Solyc00g009100.3.ITAG3.2	50
Solyc00g009110.3.ITAG3.2	98
Solyc00g009140.3.ITAG3.2	18
Solyc00g009141.1.ITAG3.2	44

Figure 3: RNA-Seq Pipeline for Transcriptome Alignment approach.

Table 3: Subset of Results for RNA-Seq analysed by the Genome Alignment approach, showing transcript ID, transcript length and mapped / unmapped fragments.

Solyc01g066580.2.1	135	0	0	Solyc11g005180.1.1	1098	2	0
Solyc08g061760.2.1	302	0	0	Solyc11g005190.2.1	981	2	0
Solyc11g005000.2.1	930	52	0	Solyc11g005200.2.1	1641	34	0
Solyc11g005010.2.1	1343	31	1	Solyc11g005210.1.1	291	0	0
Solyc11g005015.1.1	2352	25	10	Solyc11g005220.2.1	871	64	2
Solyc11g005020.2.1	1872	26	1	Solyc11g005230.1.1	1263	1	1
Solyc11g005030.2.1	3117	89	4	Solyc11g005240.1.1	1299	0	0
Solyc11g005050.2.1	538	88	6	Solyc11g005250.2.1	4817	116	6
Solyc11g005060.2.1	1498	20	2	Solyc11g005260.2.1	1292	2	0
Solyc11g005070.2.1	2522	6	0	Solyc11g005270.1.1	573	0	0
Solyc11g005080.1.1	2028	31	0	Solyc11g005280.1.1	627	6	0
Solyc11g005090.2.1	4998	39	1	Solyc11g005290.1.1	633	0	0
Solyc11g005100.2.1	3947	3	1	Solyc11g005300.2.1	1938	2	0
Solyc11g005110.2.1	2820	42	0	Solyc11g005310.1.1	645	0	0
Solyc11g005120.2.1	1339	0	0	Solyc11g005320.1.1	660	0	0
Solyc11g005130.2.1	3733	58	4	Solyc11g005330.2.1	2088	628	17
Solyc11g005140.1.1	1770	41	1	Solyc11g005340.2.1	1586	16	0
Solyc11g005150.2.1	1449	60	6	Solyc11g005350.2.1	1550	25	0
Solyc11g005160.1.1	1293	1	1	Solyc11g005360.2.1	839	44	0
Solyc11g005170.2.1	2326	374	16	Solyc11g005370.2.1	712	48	1

Table 4: Subset of Results for RNA-Seq analysed using Salmon Pseudo-Alignment.

Name	Length	EffectiveLength	TPM	NumReads
Solyc01g066580.2.1	135	13.850	0.000000	0.000
Solyc08g061760.2.1	302	90.172	0.000000	0.000
Solyc11g005000.2.1	930	692.985	47.052371	26.000
Solyc11g005010.2.1	1343	1105.969	17.009067	15.000
Solyc11g005015.1.1	2352	2114.969	5.336674	9.000
Solyc11g005020.2.1	1872	1634.969	9.971627	13.000
Solyc11g005030.2.1	3117	2879.969	18.722165	42.994
Solyc11g005050.2.1	538	301.523	187.165029	45.000
Solyc11g005060.2.1	1498	1260.969	8.950974	9.000
Solyc11g005070.2.1	2522	2284.969	1.646543	3.000
Solyc11g005080.1.1	2028	1790.969	15.178615	21.676
Solyc11g005090.2.1	4998	4760.969	3.773008	14.324
Solyc11g005100.2.1	3947	3709.969	0.000000	0.000
Solyc11g005110.2.1	2820	2582.969	10.196057	21.000
Solyc11g005120.2.1	1339	1101.969	0.000000	0.000
Solyc11g005130.2.1	3733	3495.969	10.044368	28.000
Solyc11g005140.1.1	1770	1532.969	16.361714	20.000
Solyc11g005150.2.1	1449	1211.969	28.973350	28.000
Solyc11g005160.1.1	1293	1055.969	0.000000	0.000
Solyc11g005170.2.1	2326	2088.969	110.463297	184.000
Solyc11g005180.1.1	1098	860.969	1.456615	1.000
Solyc11g005190.2.1	981	743.972	1.685681	1.000
Solyc11g005200.2.1	1641	1403.969	15.185308	17.000
Solyc11g005210.1.1	291	83.017	0.000000	0.000
Solyc11g005220.2.1	871	634.000	64.746241	32.732
Solyc11g005230.1.1	1263	1025.969	0.000000	0.000
Solyc11g005240.1.1	1299	1061.969	0.000000	0.000
Solyc11g005250.2.1	4817	4579.969	15.659658	57.189
Solyc11g005260.2.1	1292	1054.969	1.188755	1.000
Solyc11g005270.1.1	573	336.343	0.000000	0.000
Solyc11g005280.1.1	627	390.161	9.642944	3.000
Solyc11g005290.1.1	633	396.145	0.000000	0.000
Solyc11g005300.2.1	1938	1700.969	0.000000	0.000
Solyc11g005310.1.1	645	408.127	3.072818	1.000
Solyc11g005320.1.1	660	423.112	0.000000	0.000
Solyc11g005330.2.1	2088	1850.969	208.955868	308.405
Solyc11g005340.2.1	1586	1348.969	7.437384	8.000
Solyc11g005350.2.1	1550	1312.969	11.619757	12.165
Solyc11g005360.2.1	839	602.011	45.830055	22.000
Solyc11g005370.2.1	712	475.062	60.716966	23.000
Solyc11g005380.2.1	2379	2141.969	62.647360	107.000

Table 5: Subset of Results for RNA-Seq analysed using Kallisto Pseudo-Alignment.

target_id	length	eff_length	est_counts	tpm
Solyc01g066580.2.1	135	18.313	1	42.0994
Solyc08g061760.2.1	302	94.9558	0	0
Solyc11g005000.2.1	930	699.849	27	29.7437
Solyc11g005010.2.1	1343	1112.85	15	10.3918
Solyc11g005015.1.1	2352	2121.85	21	7.63028
Solyc11g005020.2.1	1872	1641.85	17	7.98273
Solyc11g005030.2.1	3117	2886.85	45	12.0178
Solyc11g005050.2.1	538	308.19	47	117.575
Solyc11g005060.2.1	1498	1267.85	11	6.689
Solyc11g005070.2.1	2522	2291.85	3	1.00919
Solyc11g005080.1.1	2028	1797.85	22.552	9.67091
Solyc11g005090.2.1	4998	4767.85	14.448	2.33626
Solyc11g005100.2.1	3947	3716.85	0	0
Solyc11g005110.2.1	2820	2589.85	25	7.4422
Solyc11g005120.2.1	1339	1108.85	0	0
Solyc11g005130.2.1	3733	3502.85	31	6.82301
Solyc11g005140.1.1	1770	1539.85	21	10.5142
Solyc11g005150.2.1	1449	1218.85	37	23.4039
Solyc11g005160.1.1	1293	1062.85	0	0
Solyc11g005170.2.1	2326	2095.85	202	74.3066
Solyc11g005180.1.1	1098	867.849	1	0.888365
Solyc11g005190.2.1	981	750.849	1	1.02679
Solyc11g005200.2.1	1641	1410.85	17	9.28975
Solyc11g005210.1.1	291	87.5524	0	0
Solyc11g005220.2.1	871	640.849	33	39.7003
Solyc11g005230.1.1	1263	1032.85	0	0
Solyc11g005240.1.1	1299	1068.85	0	0
Solyc11g005250.2.1	4817	4586.85	63	10.5892
Solyc11g005260.2.1	1292	1061.85	1	0.726061
Solyc11g005270.1.1	573	343.125	0	0
Solyc11g005280.1.1	627	396.981	4	7.7683
Solyc11g005290.1.1	633	402.981	0	0
Solyc11g005300.2.1	1938	1707.85	0	0
Solyc11g005310.1.1	645	414.94	1	1.85802
Solyc11g005320.1.1	660	429.897	0	0
Solyc11g005330.2.1	2088	1857.85	331	137.358
Solyc11g005340.2.1	1586	1355.85	9	5.11761
Solyc11g005350.2.1	1550	1319.85	12	7.00959
Solyc11g005360.2.1	839	608.849	22	27.8579
Solyc11g005370.2.1	712	481.897	24	38.3966
Solyc11g005380.2.1	2379	2148.85	111	39.8247

3.4 Epigenetics Validation

Epigenetics represents a contrasting case to transcriptomics since the wet-lab steps vary quite broadly, depending on the epigenetic property being measured. None the less, in many cases the resulting data represents a quantification of DNA captured from each genome position.

As such, the bioinformatics pipelines are correspondingly similar, involving quantification of DNA sequenced from each genomic position, and binning to reduce the number of datapoints send for downstream analysis. An example of such a pipeline is shown in Figure 4, with a subset of the corresponding results shown in Table 6.

Figure 4: Pipeline for DNA quantification-based Epigenetics Analysis.

Table 6: Subset of Results for DNA quantification-based Epigenetics Analysis, showing chromosome, start / end positions and coverage quantification.

SL3.0ch00	324500	324600	0
SL3.0ch00	324600	324700	2
SL3.0ch00	324700	324900	4
SL3.0ch00	324900	325800	0
SL3.0ch00	325800	326000	2
SL3.0ch00	326000	326300	0
SL3.0ch00	326300	326400	2
SL3.0ch00	326400	326600	1
SL3.0ch00	326600	327300	0
SL3.0ch00	327300	327400	1
SL3.0ch00	327400	327600	2
SL3.0ch00	327600	330800	0
SL3.0ch00	330800	330900	2
SL3.0ch00	330900	331000	4
SL3.0ch00	331000	331100	6
SL3.0ch00	331100	331200	4
SL3.0ch00	331200	331400	2
SL3.0ch00	331400	336900	0
SL3.0ch00	336900	337000	1
SL3.0ch00	337000	337300	2
SL3.0ch00	337300	337500	1
SL3.0ch00	337500	341000	0
SL3.0ch00	341000	341100	2
SL3.0ch00	341100	341200	4
SL3.0ch00	341200	341300	2
SL3.0ch00	341300	343000	0
SL3.0ch00	343000	343100	1
SL3.0ch00	343100	343200	2
SL3.0ch00	343200	343300	3
SL3.0ch00	343300	343500	2

4. Conclusions

It was decided to implement the raw to quantitative data processing for the GLOMICAVE platform using the Galaxy processing framework, and this approach was validated to form this Deliverable.

A local instance of Galaxy was deployed and configured to act as the pipeline development and validation platform.

Two omics, namely transcriptomics and epigenomics, were chosen to validate the proposed approach.

Multiple candidate pipelines were created and validated using data from example RNA-Seq and Chip-Seq datasets.

Next step involves integrating the results of this deliverable into the GLOMICAVE Framework as part of WP5 and connect with WP4 for downstream processing of the output of the quantitative processing pipelines. Some steps that were carried out manually for the validation are performed in an automated manner by Task 1.3. Once WP1 developments are integrated in the platform, processing a larger selection of public datasets using cloud-based computation will allow the optimal pipeline and parameters to be determined.